

Synthesis and Properties of some Disulphide Sulphinate Salts

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Manuscript received 11 September 1991, revised 25 June 1992, accepted 3 July 1992

Several disulphide sulphinate salts afford promising mammalian protection against ionisation radiation¹⁻³. The present communication reports new types of disulphide sulphinate salts obtained by reaction of four disulphide dioxide (1-4) with 5,5-dimethyl-2-thiobarbituric acid, in a search for a more potent radioprotective and antithyroidal agents. Stability of 5-8 in solution was examined, since this property is clearly important in biological administration and is chemically significant for clarification of factors involved in disproportionation to symmetrical disulphide.

The disulphide sulphinate salts (5-8) were prepared by oxodisulphide cleavage in an open-chain system, e.g. dibenzyl disulphide dioxide (1) where sulphinate moiety was knocked out while in cyclic system the sulphinate moiety was retained. Advantage of keeping sulphinate moiety intact in the molecule is believed to increase the solubility and modify the activity³. The synthesis was affected by adding equimolar quantities of thiols (as sodium salts) in methanol to an appropriate disulphide dioxide in the same solvent. Addition of large amount of dry ether precipitated the disulphide, which was again purified by reprecipitation, but disproportionation occurred within a few minutes and good analysis could not be obtained.

Results and Discussion

In all the cases, yields of the disulphides were good and products obtained were of exceptional purity. These disulphide sulphinate salts are extremely hygroscopic and readily acquire enough moisture to cause analytical problems. The structure of all these disulphide salts have been confirmed by the following evidences. Thiolate ion disappears since the solutions of thiolate salts are very basic, but after reaction with disulphide dioxides, are neutral (tlc also shows loss of thiolate ion). The strong ir absorption by $-\text{SSO}_2-$ of disulphide dioxide at 1 120 and 1 290 cm^{-1} is not seen in the products, hence disulphide dioxides are consumed as well. The products show one major tlc spot (although one to two barely visible spots were always observed owing to a small unavoidable degree of disproportionation). The products show very strong new ir bands at 940-1 040 cm^{-1} (usually as either a broad band or a doublet) as expected for the $-\text{SO}_2\text{Na}$ moiety. The disproportionation of unsymmetrical disulphide sulphinate salt (6) yielded dithiane dioxide (2) and thiolate salt. It seems that neighbouring group effect of $-\text{SO}_2-$ on disulphide linkage is important in this class of compounds.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by using a Kofler hot stage apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were obtained by using a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer. Moist extracts were dried by MgSO_4 . Dibenzyl disulphide dioxide⁴, 1,2-dithiane-1,1-dioxide⁵, 2,3-benzodithiane-2,2-dioxide³, dibenzo[*c,e*]-*o*-dithin-5,5-dioxide³ and 5,5-dimethyl-2-thiobarbituric acid⁶ were prepared by the reported methods.

Benzyl-5,5-dimethyl-4,6-dione pyrimid-2-yl disulphide (5): A solution of sodium (460 mg, 20 mg-atom) dissolved in methanol (20 ml) was added dropwise to a mixture of dibenzyl disulphide dioxide (5.56 g, 20 mmol) and 5,5-dimethyl-2-thiobarbituric acid (3.44 g, 20 mmol) in methanol (50 ml) with constant stirring for 20 min at 0-5°. The insoluble salt precipitated was filtered and the filtrate afforded disulphide by removal of solvent under reduced pressure (6 g, 62%), m.p. 160° (Found: C, 53.19; H, 4.48; N, 9.31; S, 21.61. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$, calcd. for: C, 53.06; H, 4.76; N, 9.52; S, 21.76%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 200-3 150 (NH), 1 620 (C=N), 1 660 (C=O) and 455 cm^{-1} (S-S).

Sodium [(5,5-dimethyl-4,6-dione pyrimid-2-yl) dithio]butane sulphinate (6): Sodium (460 mg, 20 mg-atom) in methanol (20 ml) was added dropwise

during 30 min to a mixture of 1,2-dithiane-1,1-dioxide (3 g, 20 mmol) and 5,5-dimethyl-2-thiobarbituric acid (3.44 g, 20 mmol) in methanol (50 ml) with constant stirring at 0–5°. After the addition was complete (15 min, the reaction of the thiol was complete by tlc), dry ether (500 ml) was added to the reaction mixture until no more precipitate formed. The solvent was then decanted and the white precipitate was dissolved in a minimum amount of methanol (10 ml). Anhydrous ether was again added until a slight turbidity resulted. The mixture was centrifuged and the clear solution so obtained was removed and diluted with ether (400 ml) to yield the product (4.2 g, 77%), m.p. 187° (Found: C, 34.96; H, 4.01; N, 7.86; S, 27.24. $C_{10}H_{15}N_2S_2O_4Na$ calcd. for: C, 34.68; H, 4.33; N, 8.09; S, 27.74 %); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 1 640 (C=O), 1 625 (C=N), 1 010 and 940 cm^{-1} (SO_2Na).

Sodium [(5,5-dimethyl-4,6-dione pyrimid-2-yl) dithiomethylphenyl]methane sulphinate (7): It was prepared from 2,3-benzodithiane-2,2-dioxide (4.0 g, 20 mmol) and 5,5-dimethyl-2-thiobarbituric acid (3.4 g, 20 mmol) and sodium (460 mg, 20 mg-atom) in methanol (20 ml), (5.2 g, 70%), m.p. 180° (Found: C, 42.40; H, 3.47; N, 6.93; S, 24.37. $C_{14}H_{18}N_2O_4S_2Na$ calcd. for: C, 42.63; H, 3.80;

N, 7.10; S, 24.36%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 200 (NH), 1 650 (C=O), 1 630 (C=N), 1 010 and 960 cm^{-1} (SO_2Na).

Sodium 2'-[(5,5-dimethyl-4,6-dione pyrimid-2-yl) dithio]-2-biphenyl sulphinate (8): Sodium (230 mg, 10 mg-atoms) dissolved in methanol was added to a mixture of dibenzo[*c,e*]-*o*-dithi-5,5-dioxide (2.48 g, 10 mmol) and 5,5-dimethyl-2-thiobarbituric acid (1.72 g, 10 mmol) in methanol (20 ml) with stirring at 0–5° afforded the product (2.5 g, 60%), m.p. 210° (Found: C, 48.76; H, 3.30; N, 6.69; S, 21.79. $C_{18}H_{18}N_2S_2O_4Na$ calcd. for: C, 48.87; H, 3.39; N, 6.33; S, 21.72%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 260 (NH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 630 (C=N), 1 020 and 950 cm^{-1} (SO_2Na).

References

1. L. FIELD and R. B. BARBEE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, 34, 1792.
2. P. K. SRIVASTAVA and L. FIELD, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1972, 37, 4196.
3. P. K. SRIVASTAVA, L. FIELD and M. M. GREANAN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1975, 18, 798.
4. O. HINSBEG, *Chem. Ber.*, 1908, 41, 2836.
5. N. ISENBER, Ph.D. Thesis, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, 1963.
6. E. MILLER, J. C. MUNCH, F. S. CROSSELY and W. H. HARTUNG, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1090.